

Factors Influencing the Formation of a Healthy Lifestyle of Medical Students

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Annotation: A study was made of the components of lifestyle and morbidity of medical Institute students, in particular, the most common problems of a student in his desire to lead a healthy lifestyle were identified. Possible ways to overcome these problems are presented.

Keywords: health, healthy lifestyle, student's daily routine, bad habits, healthy sleep, proper nutrition.

Introduction.

Human health, in the understanding of the World Health Organization, is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, and not only the absence of diseases and physical defects [1]. The article examines the attitude of students to a healthy lifestyle. A healthy and educated person is a national priority in the Republic of Uzbekistan. A healthy generation is one of the main achievements of any nation. The health of the entire nation depends on the state of human health as a citizen, which means its well-being and innovative development. The strategic importance of the health of the Uzbek people has been repeatedly emphasized by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoyev: "The health of the nation is above and most valuable" (from the decree of December 18, 2022, approved the concept and program of measures to prevent noncommunicable diseases, support a healthy lifestyle and increase the level of physical activity of the population for 2019-2024). In his speech, the Head of our state outlined 7 areas of work developed on the basis of generalization and systematization of appeals. The first direction is to bring primary medical services closer to the population, the second is to develop emergency medical care, the third is to improve conditions in medical institutions, the fourth is to provide financial incentives for workers in the field, the fifth is to provide hospitals with qualified personnel, the sixth is to increase the culture of healthy living in society, and the seventh is to prevent diseases.

In the domestic healthcare system, he noted, an approach prevails in which more attention is paid not to prevention, but to the treatment of diseases. At the same time, up to 55% of the factors affecting human health are related to lifestyle (physical activity, nutrition, bad habits), 20% to the state of the environment, the president said, referring to data from the World Health Organization.

Methodology. The concept of a "healthy lifestyle" includes many components, and its choice is influenced by many factors, both biological and social.

The purpose of the work: To study the impact of a healthy lifestyle on university education.

Tasks: To identify which lifestyle of a student can be called healthy; to determine the factors of formation of a healthy lifestyle among students; To analyze the impact of a healthy lifestyle on studying at a medical university.

According to WHO, human health depends on lifestyle by 50%, heredity by 20%, environmental conditions by 20% and health system development by 10%.[3] The main components of a healthy lifestyle are proper nutrition, physical education and sports, and the correct distribution of daily routines. The daily routine includes, among other things, regular performance of the same actions at the same time. This not only makes a person more disciplined, but also allows his body to work more

efficiently. According to experts in the field of physical culture, one of the main aspects of a healthy lifestyle is physical activity.

Discussion

From the context of the definitions of the concept of "healthy lifestyle", it follows that it implies the meaning of a way of organizing a person's life aimed at preventing diseases and promoting health.

A healthy lifestyle is one of the possible options for human life in general. Lifestyle is considered as a way of life activity inherent in a given person.

A healthy lifestyle reflects the generalized typical structure of students' life forms, which is characterized by the unity and expediency of the processes of self-organization and self-discipline, self-regulation and self-development, aimed at strengthening the adaptive capabilities of the body, the full self-realization of their strengths and abilities in general cultural and professional development, and life in general.

Traditionally, there are three types of activities: work, educational (cognitive) and gaming.[4] Depending on the stage of the life path, one of these activities becomes the main one for a person. In this case, the healthy lifestyle of students is considered.

Results

In the survey of 1st-2nd-3rd year students, the answers to the question "what factors are an obligatory component of a healthy lifestyle?" were distributed as follows: heredity – 42.7%; environment – 22.4%; lifestyle – 27.5%; medicine – 7.4%.

At the same time, students name sleep – 26.6%, nutrition – 22.1%, rest – 18.5%, mental well-being – 8.8%, hygiene - 10.1%, physical education -13.9% as favorable factors.

Students consider the following unfavorable factors: insufficient sleep time - 20.6% of respondents, lack of time - 34.6%, lack of movement - 14.2%, physical overexertion - 17.6%, smoking - 11.6%, alcohol - 8.10%, non-compliance with hygiene requirements - 4.8 %

The majority of students participating in the survey rate their health as average (62.8%), 20.6% rate their health above average, and 16.6% of respondents rate their health as high. 55.2% of respondents know about the physiological functions of organs and organ systems of their body, and 44.8% of respondents partially know. 62.4% are aware of the prevention of postural disorders, flat feet, visual and hearing disorders, and 37.6% are partially aware. 80.1% are aware of the prevention and treatment of colds, and 18.8% are partially aware. 70.7% are able to provide first aid for bleeding and injuries, 29.1% will not be able to provide assistance.

Proficiency in self-monitoring methods: 69.4% of respondents have heart rate monitoring, 40.5% do not know how to use this method of self-monitoring. 59.4% of respondents are able to assess their physical development, while 40.5% of respondents are unable to assess their physical development. 39.1% of respondents are able to assess their physical fitness, while 60.8% are unable to assess their physical fitness.

At the same time, 43.2% of respondents have chronic diseases: gastritis - 24.3%, pancreatitis - 8.1%, bronchitis - 7.4% of respondents; posture disorders - 16.2%, scoliosis - 10.8%, normal spine condition - 72.9% of respondents.

Bad habits. 33.7% of respondents smoke, of which girls - 10.8% of respondents, boys - 22.9%; smoke one cigarette a day - 14.8% , 2-3 cigarettes a day - 3.7%, 4-5 cigarettes a day 0% of respondents. They drink alcohol: once a month - 32.4% of respondents, 2 times a month -14.8%, 3 times a month - 10.8% , do not drink alcohol - 41.8% of respondents.[3]

The analysis showed that not all students are aware of the individual characteristics of their body, which is why they cannot build a rational lifestyle that fully corresponds to biological characteristics. Students do not know the methods of assessing their level of health, they cannot assess their current

condition and, depending on this, determine the optimal mode of life for themselves. Parents do not focus their children on maintaining and strengthening their health, and many families lack motivation for healthy living. It is not uncommon for parents not to condemn and even indirectly support the emergence of harmful habits in children, such as alcohol consumption and smoking. Thus, the survey results show that it is necessary to provide students with more information about a healthy lifestyle.

Following a healthy lifestyle ensures a person not only a long life, but also sufficient material well-being due to high efficiency and reduced costs of medical interventions.

The desire to lead a healthy lifestyle does not appear by itself, but is shaped by the influence of surrounding people.

The promotion of a healthy lifestyle should be focused on the emergence of a person's concept of a healthy lifestyle, and the emergence of a desire to lead it.

Based on the survey data above, few students have information about the functioning of their bodies, although most of them are familiar with the concept of a healthy lifestyle and its main components. It is important to understand the reasons why this happens and identify the factors influencing students' choice of a healthy lifestyle.

As part of a study conducted at the Andijan State Medical Institute, students' opinions on the motives that motivate them to lead a healthy lifestyle were studied. The students were asked to answer the question of what could motivate them to start leading a healthy lifestyle. More than half noted that such an impulse could be a decrease in the amount of free time (42.2%). The second most popular motivator is the possibility of weight gain in the absence of physical activity (53.6%). The third most important factor is financial: more than a third of the surveyed students would lead an active lifestyle if they had the opportunity to attend free group classes in government institutions (27.1%). Slightly less than a third of the respondents believe that they could be motivated to lead an active life by a deterioration in their health due to physical inactivity (33%) and the influence of friends (32.5%). About a quarter of the respondents mentioned the desire to change for the sake of a loved one among important factors (13.8%). Motivating information about the benefits of physical education could encourage students to be more active only in 13.5% of cases. The least effective motivators are, according to the data obtained, television programs demonstrating exercises like "Morning Walking" (5.7%) and examples of an active life based on employment (4.6%). The data obtained correlate with the results of research on the healthy lifestyle of medical students: they named lack of time (59%), weak willpower (13%), lack of necessary conditions (18%), lack of money (10%) as the reasons hindering a healthy lifestyle.[1]

In another study, students were asked what factors prevented them from leading a healthy lifestyle. 81% named the state of the environment, bad habits – 45%, heavy workload in classes – 31%, heavy workload of participation in educational events - 33%, lack of funds to maintain health – 22%, low level of promotion of a healthy lifestyle – 13%, modern pace of life – 7%, low level of medical care maintenance – 11%, heredity – 13%, heavy physical education burden – 5%.

When asked which factors of the educational process have the most negative impact, students name the following: long duration of classes – 33%, heavy mental load – 37.9%, inconvenient schedule – 30%, weak material and technical base - 29%, unsatisfactory sanitary and hygienic conditions of classrooms – 24.1%. Other factors were mentioned by 18% of students, 3% of students found it difficult to answer.[5]

In addition, another survey revealed that the majority of students are hampered by lack of strong motivation for self-recovery – 19.9%, lack of time – 20.1%, lack of conditions – 14.8%, lack of knowledge about healthy lifestyle – 7.4%, financial difficulties – 12.1%, lack of interest - 10.8%, students' opinion that diseases they are not in danger – 9.5%.[3]

You can pay attention to how often students indicate a lack of motivation and desire.

Information about the state of health has a great impact on maintaining a healthy lifestyle. According to the survey, 60.1% of respondents consider themselves perfectly healthy; 49.8% of respondents consider themselves sick, 24.8% of respondents worry about their health; 32.1% have no time to think about their health, 22.9% do not think about their health.[3]

At the heart of a healthy lifestyle, it is customary to distinguish between primary risk factors, which vary depending on social, economic, political, and natural and man-made conditions. Secondary risk factors contributing to the origin of the development of diseases, accompanied by pathological conditions. Along with the generally recognized signs, great importance is attached to indicators that allow us to assess the functional state of the body according to various physiological and biochemical changes that do not yet cause disease, but minimize the body's capabilities. The main reasons for the risk of a student's healthy lifestyle are: unfavorable working conditions, poor material and living conditions, stressful situations, extremely high urban growth, unbalanced and poor-quality nutrition, harmful habits (alcoholic beverages, smoking, the use of drugs and psychotropic substances). There are three values of the value of health and healthy lifestyle: 1) biological: primary health; 2) social: health as a measure of social activity of an individual's active attitude to the world; 3) personal (psychological): health as a means of overcoming illness [3].

The main factors shaping a healthy lifestyle are a rationally organized daily routine, optimal motor activity, outdoor physical education classes, age-appropriate tempering procedures, balanced nutrition, favorable hygienic and sanitary conditions, as well as the example of family, surrounding peers and teachers.

Higher education institutions are interested in improving student academic performance. For this purpose, events are regularly held designed to promote a healthy lifestyle, which means an improvement in the body's condition and an increase in working capacity.

Studying at a university is a stressful time in which a student not only masters professional skills, but also develops as a person.

Therefore, success during this period is very important. Its prerequisite is good health.

According to a number of scientific studies, one of the main success factors in academic activities is students leading a healthy lifestyle.[6]

Giving up bad habits, regular physical education and following other rules of a healthy lifestyle improve the functioning of all body systems, reduce stress on it and, consequently, allow you to spend more energy on education.

For example, smoking and alcohol consumption significantly weaken the nervous and cardiovascular systems, the systems that most strongly affect the ability to process information, withstand intellectual, emotional and physical stress, and irreversible cognitive impairments may occur.

Drug addiction is the most dangerous type of addiction that destroys a person's personality and significantly reduces his intellectual abilities. It is incompatible not only with successful learning, but also with the assimilation of the simplest information received in everyday life.

The absence of bad habits significantly increases the chances of being healthy and successful, but this alone is not enough. Physical activity is necessary, among other things, which strengthens the heart and blood vessels and improves the functioning of all body systems. Moreover, physical exercise often improves your emotional state and, consequently, your performance.

A healthy diet is equally important for the development of intellectual abilities. So, one of the most important vitamins, B vitamins, from childhood affect the development of the brain and its ability to perceive information. Proper nutrition allows you to get these and many other vitamins and strengthen your health. For example, meat and meat products, cereals contain vitamins B12, B1, B2, B6. Proper nutrition with reasonable use of dietary supplements allows the body to receive all the necessary substances and develop. Without proper nutrition, it is impossible to talk about a healthy lifestyle.[7]

As mentioned above, the mandatory components of a healthy lifestyle are constant monitoring of one's health, regular physical education and sports, daily routine, rejection of bad habits, hardening, rational nutrition, and compliance with hygiene standards.

According to the conducted research, the importance of a healthy lifestyle for successful education is understood not only by specialists in the field of biology and medicine, but also by students themselves.

A survey was conducted among students of the 1-3 courses of the Faculty of Medicine, the purpose of which was to identify students' attitude to a healthy lifestyle as an important factor in the success of their studies and to find out how students are ready to lead it.

The results showed that 55.8% of the surveyed students consider leading a healthy lifestyle to be the key to successful university studies, 33.7% do not think so, and 10.5% found it difficult to answer this question. The survey suggested seven components of a healthy lifestyle. At the same time, 62.3% of students consider physical education and sports to be the most important factor for successful learning, 25.7% prefer observing the daily routine, 7% – giving up bad habits, 5% – controlling their health. It is worth noting that none of the respondents indicated compliance with the diet and sanitary standards.

At the same time, 80.6% of students assume that they lead a healthy lifestyle. However, most of them specify that they follow the rules of a healthy lifestyle only partially. A very small number of students are engaged in systematic health improvement, and 19.4% of the respondents have bad habits that they cannot get rid of, although they wish to.

The students' attitude to sports turned out to be different: 72% of girls believe that physical education classes at the university are enough to maintain their health, while most of the different types of physical activity prefer aerobics. Only 28% of female students talk about the need for additional classes and call the workload received in physical education classes insufficient. The boys' attitude to sports turned out to be different. The majority (70.3%) offer volleyball (24.5%), football (18.7%), basketball (15.9%) and exercise equipment (11.2%) as means of physical education. According to the survey, only 21.5% of the young men who participated in the survey are engaged in physical education outside of the educational process. The majority (52.7%) say that they do this on an irregular basis, as much as possible, about a quarter (25.8%) of young people refer to the lack of time for such activities. At the same time, 31.2% of students would like to practice physical education three times a week, and 28.1% of respondents arrange two-day classes. For one physical education class per week, 29.5% performed.

The main reason preventing students from leading a healthy lifestyle, 68.3% of respondents cite a heavy workload and involvement in various educational activities, the need to combine it with work, 20.7% – laziness, and only 11% indicated a lack of need to maintain their health.[8]

Conclusion.

According to the survey results, the following patterns can be identified: most students are fully aware of the importance of a healthy lifestyle and its relationship to learning success. Many students strive to lead a healthy lifestyle, although they do not fulfill all its requirements. Most students support the need for physical education classes at the university, and even advocate three classes per week. Respondents cited heavy workload at school and at work as the main reason that prevents them from leading a healthy lifestyle.

A healthy lifestyle can be called one that helps to strengthen and improve the body both physically and emotionally. Its mandatory components are physical activity, proper nutrition, the absence of bad habits, and compliance with sanitary and hygienic standards.[9]

The main factors that influence the choice of a healthy lifestyle are the amount of stress, motivation, including the desire to look aesthetically pleasing, the example of loved ones and financial opportunities. The impact of a healthy lifestyle on university education is undeniable. It allows you to

better assimilate information, increases work efficiency and ability to work, and helps prevent the occurrence of diseases.

A person who leads a healthy lifestyle is often more successful in learning activities than someone who does not. Such observations are reported not only by medical experts, but also by the students themselves participating in the healthy lifestyle survey.

However, despite the fact that students are aware of the importance of maintaining and strengthening their health, most of them do not comply with all the requirements of a healthy lifestyle. The main reason for this is the heavy workload and lack of time, as well as the lack of strong motivation.

The success of students leading a healthy lifestyle is explained by minimizing the negative effects on their bodies, a sufficient amount of nutrients and, consequently, increased resistance to stress, including academic.

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